

High Dose Digoxin Intoxication Treated Successfully with Charcoal Hemoperfusion: A Case Report

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HISTORY

27 year old male, a resident doctor with past medical history of bipolar disorder presented to ER with history of consumption 45 milligrams (90 tablets of 0.5mg) digoxin tablets. Following which, after an interval of 3 hours, he developed nausea and had multiple episodes of vomiting post 6 hours of consumption. He was taken to the nearby hospital where he was treated with IV atropine, given GI lavage and was referred urgently to higher centre. Upon reaching ER, patient was restless, complained of severe nausea; clinical examination showed a pulse rate of 102/min and blood pressure of 120/80mm of mercury. Patient did not experience any episode of xanthopsia neither did he manifest any systemic findings. An emergency temporary pacemaker implantation was done under fluoroscopic guidance and a prophylactic rate of 60/min was set in case he suffers bradycardia.

INVESTIGATIONS

The hemogram was within normal limits, renal function tests showed Creatinine:1.57 , BUN:13 and serum potassium:7.6 meq/l. Serum digoxin levels >5.00 ng/ml (ref. range: 0.80-2.00ng/ml), and potassium levels were monitored 12 hourly.

HOSPITAL COURSE

After primary symptomatic management and TPI insertion, patient was shifted to intensive care unit. As the effect of atropine that the patient had received at primary care centre weaned off, patient developed bradycardia which was taken care for by the TPI set at the rate of 60/min. The potassium levels were persistently high despite of attempts to correct with IV insulin+glucose drips. Then over next 24 hours ensued the combination of changes in the ECG as a result of combined effect of high serum digoxin and hyperkalemia. QRS duration progressively prolonged, P wave flattened with progressively prolonging P-R interval as a result of increasing A-V conduction

defect. The S-T segment slurred and a more characteristic sign of digoxin effect i.e. the “hockey stick” or the “Salvador Dali sagging” appearance supervened. Patient was adequately hydrated and monitored closely for any incident arrhythmia. But looking at progressive ECG changes and fear of anticipated dysrhythmias, a more aggressive approach was planned. Due to lack of ease of availability and higher cost, treatment with IV digoxin immune FAB was found to be inconceivable. After a discussion with Nephrology team, a more practical approach was considered and patient

ECG of the patient depicting classical sign of Digoxin Effect, the classical “hockey stick or Salvador Dali’s moustache sign (red arrows)”. The black arrows point towards a premature ventricular complex suggesting of Digoxin Toxicity.

was subjected to Hemoperfusion with charcoal for 6 hours duration on day two post admission and another cycle the next day. Post two cycles of hemoperfusion, patient’s potassium levels settled down almost immediately, with a more gradual fall in serum digoxin levels over the period of next few days; both of which reflected in patients ECG with a progressive shortening in P-R interval and QRS duration to baseline values in next 72 hours, and disappearance of “hockey stick appearance” over the week. As the A-V conduction delay reduced, patient became independent of the temporary pacemaker and got back his inherent sinus rhythm. Patient was discharged post normalisation of serum digoxin values and was followed up after a week for any incident ECG changes.

DISCUSSION

Digoxin use has declined in the west since the 1990s.^[1] But, despite of advent of many novel rate control drugs, digoxin still remains one of the most widely used rate control drugs in India attributable to the fact that it is cheap, easily available and existing high prevalence of rheumatic mitral valve disease necessitating the use of digoxin as

a rate control drug for patients with atrial fibrillation.^[2] Also its inotropic ability makes it a favoured drug in instances where left ventricular function is compromised.

Although, acute digoxin toxicity is infrequent, its is common in cases of suicidal or accidental ingestion.^[3] Our patient here is a known case of bipolar disorder and with a past history of deliberate self harm. Given his medical background, he had easy access to the drug.

Digoxin increases intracellular calcium in myocardial cells indirectly, by inhibiting the sodium–potassium pump in the cell membrane. Increased intracellular calcium increases cardiac contractility, but also the risk of wide range of arrhythmias.^[4] Inhibition of this sodium-potassium ATPase causes the hyperkalemia which we saw in our case. Digoxin also causes an increase in vagal activity, reducing activity in the sinus node and prolonging conduction in the atrioventricular node and a consequent bradycardia/conduction blockade so severe, necessitating temporary pacing till its effect wears off.

The mortality rate in acute digoxin toxicity cases was as high as 20% before the introduction of digitalis-specific antibodies.^[5] Today, this rate has been reported to be as low as 5–8% in cases treated by digoxin-specific Fab fragments.^[6] Hence, the standard treatment of toxic ingestion of digoxin includes GI wash with activated charcoal(for presentation within 4 hours of ingestion),^[7] symptomatic management, atropine, anti-dysrhythmic medications, correction of hyperkalemia and temporary pacing as needed.^[8]

Since its advent in 1976, antidotal therapy with digoxin immune Fab fragments remains the best therapy for digoxin toxicity.^[9] However, first introduced in 1940s and refined subsequently in 1960s and 1970s, hemoperfusion remains mainstay of treatment of various drug overdose; especially in developing countries, with relative in-availability and higher cost of antidotal therapy.

There has been several previous reports depicting the efficacy of resin hemoperfusion in cases with toxic ingestion of lipid soluble drugs like digoxin. Our case has shown the efficacy of charcoal hemoperfusion coupled with symptomatic management, vigilant monitoring and temporary pacing in acute suicidal digoxin overdose with severe hyperkalemia where there is in-availability of resin filters and Fab immune fragments.

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